

Time Dependent solution of a two homogeneous servers Markovian Queueing system with Feedback, Environmental, Catastrophic and Restoration effects

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Abstract: In this paper we consider a finite capacity Markovian feedback queueing system with two identical servers under two environmental conditions. Change in environmental conditions also affects the state of the queueing system. Further the system is also suffered by randomly occurring disasters, which destroys all the present customers of the system in both the environmental conditions. Then a repair process is started and after the successful repair the system is ready for working. Here, repair time is known as the restoration time. After completion of their service the served customer either join at the end of the queue with probability p or permanently leave the system with probability $q = 1 - p$, this phenomenon is known as customer feedback. We modeled this queueing system and obtained the transient state solution by using probability generating function technique.

Keywords: Catastrophes, Environment, Restoration, Feedback, Finite capacity, Probability generating function.

1 Introduction

In this paper we consider simple Markovian queues that are subjected to environmental and catastrophic failures. We have considered two environmental conditions and transition from environmental conditions E to F behave like the occurrence of catastrophe. This paper is the generalization of our previous work [Darvinder et al. (2024)] in which we do not consider the concept of customers feedback. Previously we assumed that the served customer leaves the system permanently and never return back. In this paper we consider that the served customer may return back for getting service if it is not satisfied by their previous service given by the

server. Many authors have utilized the concept of feedback, restoration and catastrophes in queues see for e.g. [Rakesh (2014), Gulab (2016, 2015), Goel (1979), Jain (2006), Jain (2007), Jain (2010)]. This model finds their applications in many biological phenomenon like the birth and death of many creatures such as mosquitoes, ants, cockroaches etc. is depending upon the changes in temperature (environment) [Jain (2006)].

In the next section, we present the assumptions and definitions of the model. In section 3 and 4, we have modeled and analysed this queueing system and obtained a time dependent solution by using probability generating function technique. In section 5, further a particular case is also derived and discussed.

2 Assumptions and Definitions

- The customers arrive according to a Poisson process one by one at the service facility. We consider a non-homogeneous arrival pattern, i.e. there may exist two arrival rates, namely λ_1 and 0 of which only one is working at a time.

- The service time of two identical servers is assumed to be exponentially distributed. further, corresponding to arrival rate λ_1 the Poisson service rate is μ_1 for both the servers and corresponding to the arrival rate 0 the service rate is μ_2 for both the servers.

- The system state when operating with arrival rate λ_1 and service rate μ_1 is classified as E whereas when working with arrival rate 0 and service rate μ_2 is designated as F.

- The Poisson transition rates from environmental states F to E and E to F are denoted by θ and σ respectively.

- The catastrophe may occur according to a Poisson process with rate ζ . The effect of each occurrence makes the queue instantly empty.

- Restoration times are i.i.d random variables follows exponential distribution with parameter η . The customers are not allowed to occur during the restoration time.

- The discipline of the queue is first-come-first-served.

- After completion of their service the served customer either join at the end of the queue with probability p or permanently leave the system with probability q =1-p. Both the customers, newly arrived and feedback from the queue are served in the order in which they join at the end of the original queue. We do not consider any distinction between regular and feedback arrival.

• The capacity of the system is fixed M i.e., if at any time instant there are M customers in the queue then the new arrival will not be allowed to join the queue.

Define,

$W_{00}(t)$ represents the joint probability that the system is empty and in state E at time t without the occurrence of catastrophe.

$S_{00}(t)$ represents the joint probability that the system is empty and in state F at time t without the occurrence of catastrophe.

$W_{000}(t)$ represents the joint probability that the system is empty and in state E at time t with the occurrence of catastrophe.

$S_{000}(t)$ represents the joint probability that the system is empty and in state F at time t with the occurrence of catastrophe.

where

$$W_0 = W_{00} + W_{000} \text{ and } S_0 = S_{00} + S_{000}$$

$W_n(t)$ = Joint probability that the system is in state E and there are n customers are in the system at time t .

$S_n(t)$ = Joint probability that the system is in state F and there are n customers are in the system at time t .

$T_n(t)$ = Probability of n customers in the system at time t .

$$T_n(t) = W_n(t) + S_n(t) \quad (1)$$

Let us reckon time t from an instant when there are zero customers in the queue and the system is in the environmental state E so that the initial conditions associated with $W_n(t)$ and $S_n(t)$ becomes,

$$W_n(0) = \begin{cases} 1; & n = 0 \\ 0; & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$S_n(0) = 0; \quad \forall n \quad (2)$$

3 Equations Governing the Queueing System

$$\frac{d}{dt} W_{00}(t) = -(\lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta)W_{00}(t) + q\mu_1 W_1(t) + \theta Q_{00}(t) + \eta W_{000}(t) \quad n = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} W_{000}(t) = -(\lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + \eta)W_{000}(t) + \theta W_{000}(t) + \zeta \sum_{n=0}^M W_n(t) \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}W_1(t) = -(\lambda_1 + q\mu_1 + \sigma + \zeta)W_1(t) + 2q\mu_1W_2(t) + \theta S_1(t) + \lambda_1W_0(t); n = 1 \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}W_n(t) = -(\lambda_1 + 2q\mu_1 + \sigma + \zeta)W_n(t) + 2q\mu_1W_{n+1}(t) + \lambda_1W_{n-1}(t) + \theta S_n(t) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}W(t) = -(2q\mu_1 + \sigma + \zeta)W_M(t) + \lambda_1W_{M-1}(t) + \theta S_M(t); n = M \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}S_{00}(t) = -(\theta + \zeta)S_{00}(t) + q\mu_2S_1(t) + \sigma W_{00}(t) + \eta S_{000}(t) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}S_{000}(t) = -(\theta + \zeta + \eta)S_{000}(t) + \sigma W_{000}(t) + \zeta \sum_{n=0}^M S_n(t) \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}S_1(t) = -(q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)S_1(t) + 2q\mu_2S_2(t) + \sigma W_1(t) \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}S_n(t) = -(2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)S_n(t) + 2q\mu_2S_{n+1}(t) + \sigma W_n(t); 0 < n < M \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}S_M(t) = -(2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)S_M(t) + \sigma W_M(t); n = M \quad (12)$$

4 Transient Analysis

Let, the Laplace Transform of $f(t)$ be

$$\bar{f}(s) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} f(t) dt \quad (13)$$

Laplace transform of equations (3)-(12) with initial conditions given in (2), gives,

$$(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta)\bar{W}_{00}(s) - 1 = q\mu_1\bar{W}_1(s) + \theta \bar{S}_{00}(s) + \eta\bar{W}_{000}(s); n = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + \eta)\bar{W}_{000}(s) = \theta \bar{S}_{000}(s) + \zeta \sum_0^M \bar{W}_n(s) \quad (15)$$

$$(s + \lambda_1 + q\mu_1 + \sigma + \zeta)\bar{W}_1(s) = 2q\mu_1\bar{W}_2(s) + \theta \bar{S}_1(s) + \lambda_1\bar{W}_0(s); n = 1 \quad (16)$$

$$(s + \lambda_1 + 2q\mu_1 + \sigma + \zeta)\bar{W}_n(s) = 2q\mu_1\bar{W}_{n+1}(s) + \lambda_1\bar{W}_{n-1}(s) + \theta \bar{S}_n(s); \quad (17)$$

$$(s + 2q\mu_1 + \sigma + \zeta)\bar{W}_M(s) = \lambda_1\bar{W}_{M-1}(s) + \theta\bar{S}_M(s) \quad (18)$$

$$(s + \theta + \zeta)\bar{S}_0(s) = q\mu_2\bar{S}_1(s) + \sigma\bar{W}_0(s) + \zeta\sum_{n=0}^M\bar{S}_n(s) \quad (19)$$

$$(s + \theta + \zeta + \eta)\bar{S}_{000}(s) = \sigma\bar{W}_{000}(s) + \zeta\sum_{n=0}^M\bar{S}_n(s) \quad (20)$$

$$(s + \theta + q\mu_2 + \zeta)\bar{S}_1(s) = 2q\mu_2\bar{S}_2(s) + \sigma\bar{W}_1(s) \quad (21)$$

$$(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)\bar{S}_n(s) = 2q\mu_2\bar{S}_{n+1}(s) + \sigma\bar{W}_n(s); \quad (22)$$

$$(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)\bar{S}_M(s) = \sigma\bar{W}_M(s); \quad (23)$$

Define, The probability generating function by,

$$W(z, s) = \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s)z^n \quad (24)$$

$$S(z, s) = \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s)z^n \quad (25)$$

$$T(z, s) = \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{T}_n(s)z^n \quad (26)$$

where

$$T(z, s) = W(z, s) + S(z, s) \quad (27)$$

and

$$\bar{T}_n(s) = \bar{W}_n(s) + \bar{S}_n(s) \quad (28)$$

Multiplying equations (14)-(18) by z^n , Summing over the respective range of n and using equations (24)-(26), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & (s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)\sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s)z^n - \frac{2\mu_1}{z} [\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} \bar{W}_{n+1}(s)z^{n+1} - \\ & \bar{W}_0(s) + \bar{W}_0(s) - \bar{W}_1(s) + \bar{W}_1(s)] - \lambda_1 z [\sum_{n=1}^M \bar{W}_{n-1}(s)z^{n-1} + z^M \bar{W}_M(s) - \\ & z^M \bar{W}_M(s)] - \theta \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s)z^n - 2q\mu_1 \bar{W}_0(s) - \lambda_1 \bar{W}_M(s)z^M - 1 - \zeta \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s) - \\ & q\mu_1 z \bar{W}_1(s) - q\mu_1 \bar{W}_1(s) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)W(z, s) - \frac{2q\mu_1}{z}W(z, s) + 2q\mu_1\bar{W}_1(s) - \lambda_1zW(z, s) + \frac{2q\mu_1}{z}(1 - z)\bar{W}_0(s) - \lambda_1(1 - z)\bar{W}_M(s)z^M - \theta S(z, s) - \lambda_1z^M(1 - z)\bar{W}_M(s) - 1 - \zeta \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s) - q\mu_1z\bar{W}_1(s) - q\mu_1\bar{W}_1(s) = 0$$

$$[(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z - \lambda_1z^2 - 2q\mu_1]W(z, s) - \theta zS(z, s) + 2q\mu_1(1 - z)\bar{W}_0(s) - \lambda_1(1 - z)\bar{W}_M(s)z^{M+1} - z - z\zeta \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s) + zq\mu_1(1 - z)\bar{W}_1(s) = 0 \tag{29}$$

Similarly, from equations (19)-(23) on using equations (24)-(26), we have

$$(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta) \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s)z^n - \frac{2\mu_2}{z} [\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} \bar{S}_n(s) - \bar{S}_0(s) + \bar{S}_0(s) + \bar{S}_1(s) - \bar{S}_1(s)] - \sigma \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s)z^n - \zeta \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) - 2q\mu_2\bar{S}_0(s) - q\mu_2\bar{S}_1(s) - q\mu_2z\bar{S}_1(s) = 0$$

$$(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)S(z, s) - \frac{2q\mu_2}{z}S(z, s) + 2q\mu_2\bar{S}_1(s) + \frac{2q\mu_2}{z}\bar{S}_0(s) - \sigma W(z, s) - \zeta \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) - 2q\mu_2\bar{S}_0(s) - q\mu_2\bar{S}_1(s) - q\mu_2\bar{S}_1(s)z = 0$$

$$[2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)]S(z, s) + \sigma zW(z, s) + \zeta z \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) - 2q\mu_2\bar{S}_0(s)(1 - z) - zq\mu_2(1 - z)\bar{S}_1(s) = 0 \tag{30}$$

From equation (30), we get

$$W(z, s) = \frac{\theta zS(z, s) - 2q\mu_1(1 - z)\bar{W}_0(s) + \lambda_1(1 - z)\bar{W}_M(s)z^{M+1} + z + \zeta z \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s) - q\mu_1z\bar{W}_1(s)(1 - z)}{[z(s + \lambda_1 + 2q\mu_1 + \sigma + \zeta) - \lambda_1z^2 - 2q\mu_1]} \tag{31}$$

From equation (29), we get

$$S(z, s) = \frac{2q\mu_2(1 - z)\bar{S}_0(s) - \sigma zW(z, s) - \zeta z \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) + zq\mu_2(1 - z)\bar{S}_1(s)}{[2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)]} \tag{32}$$

Putting the value of $Q(z, s)$ in (31)

$$W(z, s) = \theta z \left[\frac{2q\mu_2(1-z)\bar{S}_0(s) - \sigma z W(z, s) - \zeta z \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) + zq\mu_2(1-z)\bar{S}_1(s)}{2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)} \right]$$

$$- 2q\mu_1(1-z)\bar{W}_0(s) + \lambda_1(1-z)\bar{W}_M(s)z^{M+1} + z + \zeta z \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s)$$

$$- q\mu_1 z \bar{W}_1(s) / [z(s + \lambda_1 + 2q\mu_1 + \sigma + \zeta) - \lambda_1 z^2 - 2q\mu_1]$$

$$W(z, s) = 2\theta zq\mu_2(1-z)\bar{S}_0(s) - \theta \zeta z^2 \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) - 2q\mu_1(1-z)\bar{S}_0(s)[2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)] + \lambda_1(1-z)\bar{W}_M(s)z^{M+1}[2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)] + z[2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)] + \zeta z \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s) [2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)] - q\mu_1(1-z)z\bar{W}_1(s)[2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)] + q\mu_2(1-z)z^2\alpha\bar{S}_1(s) / [z(s + \lambda_1 + 2q\mu_1 + \sigma + \zeta) - \lambda_1 z^2 - 2q\mu_1][2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta) + \sigma z^2 \theta]$$

(33)

Similarly, putting the value of $W(z, s)$ in equation (32), we get

$$\sigma z [\theta z S(z, s) - 2q\mu_1(1-z)\bar{W}_0(s) + \lambda_1(1-z)\bar{W}_M(s)z^{M+1} + z + z\zeta \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s) - q\mu_1 z(1-z)\bar{W}_1(s) / (s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z - \lambda_1 z^2 - 2q\mu_1] + [2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)]S(z, s) + \zeta z \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) - 2q\mu_2\bar{S}_0(s)(1-z) - 2q\mu_2\bar{S}_1(s)(1-z) = 0$$

$$\{\sigma\theta z^2 + [2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)][(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z - \lambda_1 z^2 - 2q\mu_1]\}S(z, s) = 2q\mu_1(1-z)\sigma z \bar{W}_0(s) + 2q\mu_2(1-z)[(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z - \lambda_1 z^2 - 2q\mu_1]\bar{S}_0(s) - \sigma\lambda_1(1-z)\bar{W}_M(s)z^{M+2} - \sigma z^2 - \sigma z^2 \zeta \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s) + \zeta z [\lambda_1 z^2 + 2q\mu_1 - (s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z] \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) + zq\mu_2\bar{S}_1(s)(1-z)[(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z - \lambda_1 z^2 - 2\mu_1] + q\mu_1 z^2(1-z)\sigma \bar{W}_1(s) = 0$$

$$S(z, s) = 2q\mu_1(1-z)\sigma z \bar{W}_0(s) + 2q\mu_2(1-z)[(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z - \lambda_1 z^2 - 2q\mu_1]\bar{S}_0(s) - \sigma\lambda_1(1-z)\bar{W}_M(s)z^{M+2} - \sigma z^2 - \sigma z^2 \zeta \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s) + \zeta z [\lambda_1 z^2 + 2q\mu_1 - (s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z] \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) + zq\mu_2\bar{S}_1(s)(1-z)[(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z - \lambda_1 z^2 - 2\mu_1] + q\mu_1 z^2(1-z)\sigma \bar{W}_1(s) = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+2q\mu_1)z] \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) + q\mu_1 z^2(1-z)\sigma \bar{W}_1(s) + zq\mu_2(1-z)[(s + \lambda_1 \\
 &+ \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z - \lambda_1 z^2 - 2q\mu_1] \bar{S}_1(s) / \sigma \alpha z^2 + [2q\mu_2 - z(s \\
 &+ 2q\mu_2 \theta + \zeta)] [(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + 2q\mu_1)z - \lambda_1 z^2 - 2q\mu_1]
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{34}$$

Now from equation (27), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 T(z, s) = & [\theta z + q\mu_2(s + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta + q\mu_1)z - \lambda_1 z^2 - q\mu_1] 2q\mu_2(1-z) \bar{S}_0(s) \\
 & + \zeta z \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) [\lambda_1 z^2 - z(s + \lambda_1 + q\mu_1 + \sigma + \zeta) + 2q\mu_1 - \theta z] + (1 \\
 & - z) \bar{W}_0(s) 2q\mu_1 [z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta) - 2q\mu_2 + z\sigma] + (1-z) \bar{W}_M(s) \lambda_1 [z^{M+1} 2\mu_2 \\
 & - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta) - \sigma z^{M+2}] + \zeta z \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s) [2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta) \\
 & - \sigma z] + z[2q\mu_2 - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)] - \sigma z^2 + \bar{W}_1(s) zq\mu_1(1-z)[z\sigma - [2q\mu_2 \\
 & - z(s + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta)]] + zq\mu_2(1-z) \bar{S}_n(s) [z\theta + z(s + 2q\mu_1 + \lambda_1 + \zeta + \sigma) \\
 & - 2q\mu_1 - \lambda_1 z^2] / -z^2 s^2 + s[\lambda_1 z^3 - z^2(\lambda_1 + 2q\mu_1 + 2q\mu_2 + \theta + \sigma + 2\zeta) \\
 & + z(2q\mu_1 + 2q\mu_2)] - z^2 \zeta(\sigma + \theta + \zeta) + (1-z)[-z^2 \lambda_1(2q\mu_2 + \theta + \zeta) \\
 & + z[2\theta q\mu_1 + 2q\mu_2(2q\mu_1 + \lambda_1 + \sigma + \zeta)] - 4q\mu_2 \mu_1]
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{35}$$

The unknown quantities in equation (35) are determined as follows:

Setting $z=1$, in equations (33) and (34) respectively, we have

$$W(1, s) = \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{W}_n(s) = \frac{(s+\alpha+\zeta)}{s(s+\sigma+\theta+\zeta)} \tag{36}$$

$$S(1, s) = \sum_{n=0}^M \bar{S}_n(s) = \frac{\sigma}{s(s+\sigma+\theta+\zeta)} \tag{37}$$

Equation (35) is a polynomial in z and exists for all values of z , including the three zeros of the denominator. Hence, the quantities of interest i.e. $\bar{W}_0(s)$, $\bar{S}_0(s)$ and $\bar{T}_M(s)$ are obtained by setting the numerator equal to zero and substituting the three zeros a_1, a_2, a_3 (say) of the denominator (at which the numerator must vanish).

The various state probabilities of the number of customers in the form of Laplace transform can be picked up from equation (35) as the coefficient of different powers of z .

5 Particular Case

Now taking $\theta \rightarrow \infty$, $\sigma \rightarrow \infty$ and setting $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu$ (say) with no feedback customer in relation (35), we have

$$t(z, s) = 2\mu(1 - z)\bar{T}_0(s) - \lambda_1 z^{M+1}(1 - z)\bar{W}_M(s) + z(1 - z)\mu\bar{T}_1(s) - \frac{\zeta z}{s} / \lambda_1 z^2 - z(s + \lambda_1 + 2\mu + \zeta) + 2\mu$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{T}_0(s) &= \bar{W}_0(s) + \bar{S}_0(s) \\ t(z, s) &= \lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} [\lim_{\theta \rightarrow \infty} T(z, s)] \end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

Equation (38) is a polynomial in z and exists for all values of z , including the two zeros a_1 and a_2 (say) of the denominator. Hence, the values of T_0 and W_M can be obtained by setting the numerator equal to zero.

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